

ACTIVE THERMOGRAPHY AS AN EVALUATION METHOD OF DELAMINATIONS IN COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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1 Introduction

There is a steady increase in the use of the high performance composite materials within the aerospace, naval, automotive industry, etc. This is due to their high mechanical properties, mainly, specific strength and stiffness. In addition, it is possible to tailor these properties in order to obtain different directional characteristics. This situation creates new opportunities for the elevation of the reliability and design of the modern structures. Unfortunately, composite materials are prone to numerous modes of failures, such as fiber breakage, fiber debonding, matrix cracking and the delamination. These failure mechanisms can interact and develop, significantly lowering properties of the structural components [1-5].

The damages arise from the manufacturing processes or subsequent maintenance. Generally, a low energy impact events occurring during operation can be the result of the tool drop, debris impact, bird strikes, ballistic projectiles or even accidents. Presence of cracks in elements made of the composite materials increase their manufacturing costs and/or elongate the out of service time. Additionally, there is high probability, that in many cases subsurface flaw remain undetected, which can result in the risk of the human health or life. Therefore, there is highly desirable demand for development of the effective nondestructive testing methods (NDT) for the detection and evaluation of the subsurface defects both composites and traditional materials. In this work, attention is focused mainly on fibrous composite materials. The most popular techniques of NDT are listed in *Table 1*, including some of their advantages. Among the existing approaches to the problem of the failure in

composite materials, recently, infrared thermography (IRT) emerged as the fast, non-contact and accurate method for assessing and monitoring subsurface flaws. Furthermore, the development of cracks can be also inspected [6-8].

A large amount of research studies has been conducted using various IRT techniques in the evaluation of the real and artificial defects – see e.g. Refs [8-13].

The aim of present work is the following: to evaluate the delaminations in composite structures, both artificial and developed during tests, by the infrared thermography. Two cases are considered: 1) the structure was unloaded and 2) the structure was loaded by compression.

The outline of this paper is organized as follows: a brief introduction to the topic. This is followed by the presentation of the infrared thermography methods and thermal properties of the composites. Then, detailed discussion of the specimen design, manufacturing process and test procedures is conducted. Finally, test results are discussed and conclusions are drawn.

Table 1: Currently employed methods for detection and evaluation of the defects in composite materials.

Method:	Contact type	Possible automation	Efficiency
Acoustic emission	fluid/solid	normal	high
Ultrasound	fluid	high	low
Visual techniques	air	high	high
Tomography	air	normal	low
Thermography	air	high	high

2 Infrared thermography

Basically, thermography is a process that allows us to study a part of the electromagnetic spectrum which is caused by the infrared radiation. Using heat measurement theory, non-contact temperature detection is possible.

Generally, methods of the infrared testing can be divided into active and passive techniques. The difference is in a heat excitation. In the first case the investigated object does not require external supply of energy, unlike active procedures which need additional stimulation of heat.

Passive thermography used to detect undesired deviations employs the temperature of the examined object during its normal operation or immediately after the end of its work, when temperature contrast on the surface may indicate a possible damage. Defects radiate or absorb the heat resulted from the mechanical or thermal loads, occurred during the operation of examined object, so they can be identified by passive methods. Advantages of this configuration is direct on-site interpretation of the results.

Since infrared thermography is a high-speed, portable and large area inspection technique, it has found applications in wide variety of disciplines, i.e., in building inspection, control of industrial processes, maintenance of power plants, damage detection, etc. External energy stimulation is used to test the investigated objects by active thermography. To reveal hidden flaws by this type of methods, dynamic temperature field (heating or cooling) is generated. This is due to equal temperature of the defective and healthy area of examined material.

It should be noted, that due to the thermophysical properties of composite materials, examination of internal defects, damages or properties is more effective by means of these techniques. General classification of active thermography methods is given below:

- a) type of a thermal stimulation,
- b) form and size of the induced area,
- c) arrangement of the test equipment.

IRT methods use various sources of thermal stimulation: an optical radiation, Eddy currents, an electric power, an extremely high frequency radiation, an internal heating/cooling by gas or fluid, an external heating or cooling air and mechanical

vibrations. As source of needed energy is chosen dependently on determinants, such as an efficiency, a required energy density, a price, thermophysical properties of the examined material, a possibility and/or an importance of optical disturbance.

In addition, an excitation can be done by internal sources of energy. Thermal stimulation by internal heat sources (i.e., mechanical stimulation) reveal a lack of optical distortions, and the temperature anomalies occur only in areas containing defects due to friction of cracked walls, creating zones of plastic deformation and other mechanical effects.

Active thermography methods are determined by area of heating, which can be in the form of: a point, a line or all surfaces. During heating the investigated object by the point and a continuous scanning of the surface the temperature is recorded with a certain delay which depends on the depth at which the defect occurs. This way is especially useful to detecting flaws located perpendicular to the surface of the tested object. During linear heating object warms up in a long narrow strip, which moves across the component. This method is particularly helpful in the detection of cracks located vertically to the surface of the tested object. However, the most common method is heating the entire surface. All listed possibilities have own advantages and disadvantages, mainly associated with the efficiency. The arrangement of the heat generator and recording equipment could be done by two schemes: one and two sided. It has influence to measurement in point of view of practical application. With this setting arise some advantages and disadvantages: uniformity of heating, noises, applications. Furthermore, tested object can be stimulated by cooling or heating but more practical is heating. The highest power density in zone of tested object provides optical radiation, for instance: halogen lamps.

In the point of view of the data processing and analysis, active thermography methods can be classified as: pulsed thermography (PT), lock-in thermography (LT), vibrothermography (VT) and pulse phase thermography (PPT) – see Refs [14-18].

2.1. Pulsed thermography

The pulsed infrared thermography is currently the most popular among others thermographic methods to test materials due to its quickness of inspection

and ease of interpretation of the data. Therefore, it was chosen to current investigation.

Generally, this technique uses a thermal excitation source to rapidly heat the surface of the investigated component, then, a highly sensitive infrared camera records series of thermograms at regular intervals of time of the surface both during heating and cooling stages. It should be noted, the pulse duration must be chosen carefully to prevent failure of investigated materials. The sub-surface flaws affect the way in which heat is conducted into the material, resulting in time-dependent temperature variations on the surface. Results are visualized through the creation of thermal images (thermograms) which map the temperature distribution on the surface of the examined object [14-20]. This process is schematically illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Principle of the pulsed thermography [20].

2.2. Lock-in thermography

This method uses thermal wave analysis. In contrast to PT, the specimen is stimulated with a periodic energy source. The detector of infrared radiation remotely records oscillating temperature field on the surface of tested object. The exact time dependence between the recorded temperature signal and reference signal is monitored. During each heating cycle the infrared camera records four data points what allows to reconstruct the thermal wave and to establish values of the amplitude and the phase for each pixel within the field of view, thus three images are provided: the thermogram, which is a map of the temperature distribution on the surface, phasegram connected with propagation time of thermal wave

through material (delay between stimulating heat flow and temperature fields generated as a response to this agitation) and amplitude image, which is related to the thermal diffusivity. Non-uniform conditions of heating, emissivity variations, reflections or surface geometry strongly affect on thermograms, while phasegram is relatively independent [14-18]. The experimental set-up necessity to this kind of investigation is quite similar to this one illustrated in Fig. 1.

2.3. Vibrothermography

The vibrothermography is based on the effect of conversion of externally induced mechanical vibrations into a thermal energy. In particular, a heat is generated by rubbing of internal micro walls of defects, plastic deformations, which occur when cracks begin to propagate or viscoelastic losses generated in some materials, these losses are larger in regions of stress concentration. The tests should be conducted in the elastic range. Surface and near surface defects, such as cracks and delamination are detected by means of observations superficial temperature field induced by vibrations see Refs [14-18].

2.4. Pulse phase thermography

The pulse phase thermography analysis involves the advantages of both the pulse and the modulated lock-in thermography. This approach joins the impulse acquisition procedure of the pulse thermography with the phase/frequency ideas of lock-in thermography for which samples are subjected to a periodical excitation. Similarly as in the pulse thermography the surface is stimulated by a heat impulse and the temperature decay in time domain is recorded through a sensitive IR camera. The heat impulse launched into the sample generates thermal waves of various amplitudes and frequencies in a transient mode. The transition between time domain and the frequency domain involves the Fourier transform and finally the phase or the magnitude images are presented as in the lock-in analysis instead of thermal images for various frequencies. The pulse phase thermography allows obtaining coherent information in term of frequencies instead of the thermal contrast method used in pulse thermography [14-18].

3. Thermal properties of investigated constituents

The discrepancies of the temperature distributions on the surfaces of the investigated specimens by PT are caused by the different thermal conductivities of the composite material and the inserted artificial model of the delamination. In essence, owing to these differences, it is possible to reveal subsurface discontinuities. However, real delamination is a void of air with lower thermal conductivity than widely used model of the delamination in the form of Teflon foil. Additionally, fibrous composites besides anisotropic nature of their mechanical properties have also different thermal properties in various directions.

Table 2: Thermal conductivities of selected materials.

Material	Thermal conductivity λ [W/m K]
Air (for a thin layers) [20]	0,070
Teflon [21]	0,259
GFRP (Transverse) [22]	0,350

In Table 2, thermal conductivity factors for selected materials are given. It should be noted, that thermal conductivity can vary with the increase of the temperature and can be dependent of the direction in anisotropic materials. Therefore, presented values are given for particular cases of examined constituent.

As can be seen, thermal conductivities of GFRP (Glass Fibre Reinforced Plastics) and Teflon foil are comparable, but despite this low difference, it has noticeable influence on heat transport within the investigated specimen. Comparing real delamination to its model, it can be seen that values of thermal conductivities of the thin layers of the air and the Teflon foil are considerably different. Pulsed thermography works correctly with such as small differences of thermal conductivities between Teflon inserts and fibrous composite materials. It means that this technique will be more sensitive to detect real delaminations and the effect will be enhanced.

4 Materials and methods

The specimens were manufactured from 8 plies of Hexcel TVR 380 M12/R-glass unidirectional prepreg layers. The geometry of specimens was cylindrical with a nominal thickness equal 2 mm, the length 300 mm and the inner radius 92 mm (Fig. 2). The laminate had a nominal fibre volume of 60% and the ply thickness equals 0,25mm.

To provide compromise between realistic representation and ease of preparation the delamination, Teflon film in the form of a single square was introduced during the manufacturing stage in the middle of the laminate specimens between 4th and 5th layer. Position of these inserts in relation to specimens is shown in Fig. 2. Additionally, to minimize the end effect and to prevent crushing, both ends of investigated specimens were encased in steel matrices and the epoxy resin.

Fig. 2. The geometry of the specimen and dimensions of the artificial delaminations.

All investigated specimens had three types of the stacking sequence denoted as A, B, C or D configurations with different sizes and thicknesses of the delaminations. Details are described in Table 3.

Table 3: Configurations of the examined specimens.

Denotation	Stacking sequence	Geometry of a delamination [mm]	Thickness of a delamination [μ m]
A	$[0/90/0/90]_s$	Square 60x60	25
B	$[0/90/0/90]_s$	Rectangular 10x60	25
C	$[90]_8$	Square 10x10	400
D	$[0]_8$	Square 10x10	400

The material properties were taken from characterization tests performed at the Lublin University of Technology. They are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4: Material properties for TVR 380 M12/R-glass

Elastic properties [GPa]		Strength parameters [MPa]	
E_{11}	46,43	X_t	1534
E_{22}	14,92	$Y_t=Z_t$	74,50
ν_{12}	0,269	S_{12}	57,55
G_{12}	5,233		

In order to ensure high quality of the specimens and repeatability of the manufacturing process, all laminates were cured in the autoclave at 135 °C for 120 min at 4,5 bar of the pressure and 0,8 bar of the partial vacuum. Additionally, to minimize the residual stresses generated during the production and arising from the anisotropy of the thermal expansion of the composite materials, heating and cooling stages were done at 2 °C per minute. This process is schematically illustrated in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Diagram of the manufacturing process of the examined specimens.

The system used in this study consists of Flir A325 camera with a frame rate of 60 Hz and a focal plane array pixel format of 320x240, the halogen lamp, the computer and the trigger box. The entire process is controlled by using IR-NDT software. The same program is used to the processing of the acquired data. Fig. 4 shows the complete experimental setup used in the current investigation.

To monitor possible delamination growth increment, specimens should be subjected to the thermographic

analysis during each step of loading. Furthermore, tests were monitored using a standard camera.

Fig. 4. Experimental setup.

The cylindrical panels were also tested in an loading machine with manual displacement control. In all tests, the load was applied in the axial direction at ambient conditions. Each examined specimen was instrumented with three strain gauges in order to evaluate uniformity of load. The data was acquired and processed throughout the tests by measuring amplifier HBM MGCplus and personal computer with the dedicated software CATMAN. Configuration of the loading test apparatus is presented in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. The loading test apparatus for the two-edge clamped boundary condition.

5. Results and discussion

5.1. Artificial delamination

First part of this work was devoted to the detection and location of the artificial damage for the unloaded structure. For this purpose a pulsed infrared thermography method was used. Additionally, based on the distribution of temperatures in selected areas, thickness and sizes of the embedded defects was evaluated. Fig. 6 shows the representative thermograms obtained during the heating of the unloaded specimens with the inserted defects for all investigated configurations. In the thermal images of the A and B configurations, shapes of the artificial delaminations are barely visible unlike to the C and D configurations where cracks can be easily detect.

Hot spot in the thermal image of the D configuration in Fig. 6 is caused by reflection of external emitter. Three others thermograms in Fig. 6 are free of the measurement distortion.

The detection of the temperature variations was observed at two chosen points: P_1 and P_2 presented schematically in Fig. 2. The correlation between the changes of the temperature of the specimen and the thicknesses of Teflon inserts can be observed. Fig. 7 demonstrate the distribution of the temperature with time at these two points for various configurations of investigated specimens. Obtained maximal and minimal temperatures throughout the thermographic analysis of the each run and the differences at the maximum thermal contrast for chosen points are given in Table 5.

Table 5: Maximal, minimal and differences of the temperatures for points P_1 and P_2 .

Configu- ration	Maximal temperature [°C]	Minimal temperature [°C]	Maximal difference [°C]
A	48,01	24,56	0,60
B	48,05	24,85	0,57
C	48,13	24,24	3,17
D	48,08	24,28	3,01

Fig. 6. Thermograms of the unloaded specimens with the embedded defects for all investigated configurations .

Fig. 7. Temperature variations versus time for all investigated configurations.

5.2. Effects of the delamination growth

Further analysis was carried out under various loading condition represented by the values of the displacements of the boundary plates measured in mm, since the cylindrical panel was compressed in order to investigate the opening of the artificially delaminated area. Values giving in *Table 6* describes the critical end-shortening of the specimens for examined configurations.

Table 6: Values of the Critical end-shortening of the investigated specimens.

Denotation	Stacking sequence	Critical end-shortening value [mm]
A	[0/90/0/90] _s	2,39
B	[0/90/0/90] _s	3,05
C	[90] ₈	1,43
D	[0] ₈	1,50

For C and D configurations, artificially introduced delamination was not expands during compressive mechanical loading till the final failure, therefore to the further considerations the most representative example in the form of A Configuration was taken into account.

Fig. 8. Thermogram of the loaded specimen with the defects for A configuration.

Fig. 8 provides thermal image of the A configuration made after the loading the specimen by the end-shortening equals 2,39 mm. It is clearly seen that propagation of the artificial delamination within the specimen is not uniform, therefore, thermogram have been divided into three areas denoted as A1, A2 and A3 with different level of the defected region.

Fig. 9. Temperature variation versus time for three selected areas of A configuration for end-shortening equals 2,39 mm.

The correlation between the temperature variations of the selected areas and the level of the damage can be observed - Fig. 9. The most delaminated region has the lowest temperature distribution (A3) in contrast to the less damaged (A1). According to the prior consideration it is caused by different thermal properties of composite materials, Teflon insert, voids of air (real delamination) and the interactions of the various failure mechanisms occurring in fibrous composite materials.

5.3 Deformation of the specimens

Next step of the investigation concerned analysis of the strains variation and the out of plane displacement w in the center of the artificial delamination – Fig. 2. Arrangement of the strain gauges: T1, T2 and T3, is presented in Fig. 5. Comparison between the measured microstrains and the out of plane displacements as a function of the end-shortening is given in Fig. 10.

Uniform strain distribution is provided to 0,8 mm of the end shortening displacement, then, due to geometrical imperfection of the investigated specimen and test apparatus started to increase the difference in measured strains and exceeded acceptable threshold of the 5%.

Fig. 10. Variations of the strains and the out of plane displacement as a function of the end-shortening for A configuration.

6 Conclusions

The present study emphasized the ability of the pulsed thermography to detect, locate and evaluate of the delamination (artificial and developed during the tests) within GFRP cylindrical panels with different stacking sequences and subjected to an axial compression. Additionally, current methods of the Infrared Thermography were presented.

The obtained results proved the effectiveness of used technique and provide further information for active infrared thermography as a viable nondestructive evaluation tool for testing of composite materials.

In addition, it was noted that despite of anisotropic nature of investigated specimens, influence of the stacking sequence to detection of the delamination is negligible for PT.

Furthermore, infrared thermograph should be compared to another full-field non-destructive evaluation techniques such as tomography or ultrasound to further confirm the findings of this study.

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